

“I had no idea that I was such an asshole to myself.” – Exploring positive long-term effects of Nonviolent Communication (NVC) training on researchers’ self-compassion and ability to cope with conflict

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Purpose

Between June 2020 and December 2021, I taught six courses on stress management via the Max Planck Academy. I chose Nonviolent Communication (NVC) as the methodological approach to this topic, although this was not, to my knowledge, included as an approach in the literature on training approaches to stress management and resilience. The reason for choosing this approach nonetheless was that NVC, if well taught and received, integrates three major areas related to stress management that are usually taught as different approaches or topics: (1) emotion- and problem-centred approaches (2) mindfulness and compassion approaches, and (3) conflict management approaches. And yet, NVC is usually taught in other contexts than stress management. In addition to being associated with mediation and managing conflict, NVC, to many, comes across as esoteric or “woolly”, as one participant put it.

Choosing NVC as an approach was an experiment and felt quite risky to me at the beginning. When, at the end of each six-week course, participants told me about the positive effects that it had on their mental health, I often found myself deeply moved – and curious about what it was exactly that they had learned, what had enabled that learning, and how it had improved their relationship to stress in their everyday lives in different research institutes across Germany.

By sharing and discussing feedback gathered in informal interviews with 13 former course participants, the purpose of this paper is to explore the effect that NVC had on these participants’ dealing with stressful situations and life phases. The implications suggest that NVC can be a way for individuals who suffer from the systemic uncertainty, competition, self-exploitation, and hierarchical dependencies in academic research, to increase their sense of internal freedom and safety as well as their confidence to communicate their needs in their work context.

Design

The anecdotal evidence for this paper was gathered in 13 individual recorded interviews led by me. At least one participant from each of the six courses offered via the Max Planck Academy between June 2020 and December 2021 was interviewed. The interviewees’ countries of origin are Germany, Syria, France, India, the Netherlands, Italy, Mexico, and Romania. While participating in the course, they were members of or affiliated to one of the 86 Max Planck Institutes, engaged in doctoral or postdoctoral research in a wide variety of disciplines.

The interviews took place between 1st and 14th of March 2022 via Zoom. Each interview consisted of the same questions. The answers transcribed and presented in this paper were chosen based on their significance for the hypothesis that NVC can help researchers cultivate internal safety and freedom, and communicate with more confidence, despite the systemic challenges of research careers, including both answers that do and do not support the hypothesis. The selected answers were then grouped according to common denominators, thus identifying seven components of the course that had an impact on the interviewees' learning process.

Results

The interview extracts chosen for this paper relate to one or several of the following seven components. While components 2-6 are directly related to the NVC framework of the four steps, components 1 and 7 can be seen as expected corollaries of practicing NVC both inside and outside of the course group.

1. Safe space in community experienced through opening up and deep listening to others
2. Self-empathy and empathy
3. Becoming mindful of own feelings and needs
4. Becoming aware of violent inner (self-) talk
5. Separating needs from strategies/ solutions
6. Changing communication behaviour with others
7. Distinguishing one's circle of influence from external conditions (in research) that cannot be controlled or changed by the individual

Implications

Learning NVC can be an effective way for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers to regulate their internal stress reactions while being part of a system that requires them to be high-performing, geographically mobile, navigating through extraordinary dependency on their supervisors, coping with the uncertainty of research outcomes and long-term career perspectives. One reason may be that NVC integrates problem- and emotion-centred approaches, mindfulness approaches, and conflict management approaches. Indeed, the more of the seven identified components one individual had experienced in action in their own life (as embodied experience during or after the training), the more positive was the self-reported effect that NVC had on their mental health.

From a teaching perspective, it would be interesting to learn if and how changing the course design would allow more participants to experience fully the benefits of NVC. An additional challenge might be the reconciliation between the analytical thinking (and purported preference to stay clear of emotions) associated with researchers on the one hand, and the often negative associations with the term Nonviolent Communication on the other, (falsely) linking it to the realm of the esoteric or simply dismissing it as irrelevant to mental health.

Of the seven components, the experience of a safe space of community, where people practiced deep listening and showing themselves as authentic and vulnerable, was the most frequently named. Further investigation into the necessary intra- and interpersonal behaviours of

those involved as well as the organisational and institutional structures that enable the experience of empathy, safety and community could prove highly beneficial to researchers' mental health.

Finally, the evidence gathered for this paper calls for incentivising researchers in leadership and higher management positions, such as supervisors, group leaders, PIs and directors, to train their empathy and communication skills, rather than placing the responsibility solely on the shoulders of those in lower power positions.